

The Influence of Social Media on Online Impulsive Buying Behavior: A Case Study on the Community of Mataram City

Yusi Faizathul Octavia^{a*} & M. Prajati^b

^a STIE AMM Mataram, Jl. Pendidikan No.1 Gomong, Kota Mataram, NTB 83126, Mataram, Indonesia

^b Warung Data MVDW, Jl. TGH. Nuruddin Gg. Kav. Gegutu Dayan Aik Desa Kekeru Kec. Gunungsari, Kab. Lombok Barat, NTB 83351, Mataram, Indonesia

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ABSTRACT

The aim of this research is to evaluate the influence of Social Media, comprising Hedonic Motivation, Attractiveness, Electronic Word of Mouth, Trustworthiness, and Website Quality, on Impulsive Buying. An associative research design was adopted as the study's framework. Purposive sampling technique was used to distribute 100 copies of the research instrument to social media users in Mataram city. Out of the 100 distributed questionnaires, all were filled out and returned to the researcher. Multiple linear regression analysis using SPSS software was employed to analyze the data collected from the respondents. The research findings indicate that Hedonic Motivation, Attractiveness, Electronic Word of Mouth, Trustworthiness, and Website Quality significantly influence Impulsive Buying at a level of 0.000. The results of the study reveal that four (4) significant variables affect Impulsive Buying. Furthermore, the Trustworthiness variable has been proven to be dominant, whereas Hedonic Motivation does not have a significant impact on Impulsive Buying.

1. Introduction

In the current digital era, social media has become one of the most dominant platforms in people's daily lives. Social media has transformed the way communication, interaction, and also consumer purchasing are conducted. One phenomenon that has emerged as a result of social media penetration is impulsive buying behavior.

Impulsive buying is an unplanned purchase characterized by a sudden, irresistible, and hedonically complex behavior with a lack of consideration, alternative contemplation, and self-reflection (Beatty & Ferrell, 1998). Furthermore, the impulsive buying is reflected as an irrational desire and may be considered as an intention to buy without prior planning (Chung et al., 2017). Beatty & Ferrell (1998) further define it as "a state of desire experienced upon encountering an object in the environment."

Impulsively buying serves as a rational surrogate for actual consumer impulsive buying behavior, as consumers' urge to buy impulsively leads to real impulsive purchases (Rook, 1987). Several studies have suggested using proxies for actual consumer impulsive buying behavior, particularly in the context of online and social commerce environments (Chen et al., 2016). Therefore, this research focuses on the influence of social media on impulsive buying. Social

media has opened new opportunities for marketers and businesses to influence consumer purchasing decisions by continually showcasing products, brands, and special offers through engaging content.

Online business also offers numerous benefits such as the absence of direct service interactions and tends to have lower social pressures. As noted by Dawson & Kim (2009), consumers tend to prefer online shopping over in-store shopping. The convenience of online shopping undoubtedly further motivates consumers to engage in impulsive buying when making purchase decisions (Dawson & Kim, 2009). This trend has motivated researchers to pay attention to online impulse buying (Park et al., 2012).

Several researchers (Kazi et al., 2019; Al-Zyoud, 2018; Bansal & Kumar, 2018) have indicated that the impulsive buying process is driven by emotions and that hedonic motivation influences consumers to engage in online impulsive buying behavior. Furthermore, studies have shown a positive relationship between impulsive buying and hedonic motivation (Akram et al., 2017). It is argued that hedonic consumers tend to make impulsive purchases. According to Akram et al., (2017), hedonic motivation strongly influences online impulsive buying.

* Corresponding author. STIE AMM Mataram, Jl. Pendidikan No.1 Gomong, Kota Mataram, NTB 83126, Mataram, Indonesia.

E-mail addresses: yusi.octavia@gmail.com (Y. F. Octavia).

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Koay et al., (2021) found that attractiveness had a significant positive influence on online impulse buying. That is indicating followers were more likely to engage in online impulse buying towards products and services advertised by social media influencers perceived as attractive. Similarly, Varghese & Chitra (2022) stated that attractiveness significantly influences online impulsive buying.

Furthermore, according to Husnain et al., (2016) the significant influence on impulsive buying behavior is higher in the case of electronic word-of-mouth. This statement is also supported by the findings of Koay et al., (2021); Sharma (2020); and Kazi et al., (2019) which state that electronic word-of-mouth significantly affects customers' purchase intentions. Electronic word-of-mouth is highly crucial in the realm of social media due to several reasons why a company needs to share content, besides increasing company value, creating corporate identity, and expanding the market network (Lestari, 2020).

Trustworthiness also attracts customers to purchase products and encourages them to buy without prior planning (Bansal & Kumar, 2018). The results of the analysis in the studies by Varghese & Chitra (2022); Koay et al., (2021); Kazi et al., (2019) indicate that trustworthiness on social media marketing can easily increase the level of impulsive buying behavior considering the opportunities offered by social media that can assist customers in deciding whether to make a purchase decision. Al-Zyoud (2018) asserts that within the context of social commerce, users are more likely to trust, demonstrate commitment, and feel satisfied with the services provided by service providers if the relationship between the social media site and the user is strong.

Electronic impulsive buying usually takes place on a marketplace and e-commerce websites, where social networking sites are utilized for conducting commercial activities. The study by Varghese & Chitra (2022) has shown that the quality of a website has an impact on electronic impulsive buying. According to Bansal & Kumar (2018), an attractive design of social media sites would more easily stimulate consumers' impulsive buying when products or services are offered through social media. Similarly, Al-Zyoud (2018) suggests that web quality significantly affects users' electronic impulsive buying behavior on social media platforms.

Impulsive buying behavior is significantly influenced by several variables as outlined, such as hedonic motivation, attractiveness, electronic word of mouth, trustworthiness, and website quality. This study aims to reconfirm findings from prior research. Additionally, this research also aims to analyze how these five variables impact customer purchase intentions, with a focus on customers in the Mataram city region.

Mataram City, as one of the largest cities on the island of Lombok – Indonesia, is also not exempt from the influence of social media in shaping its consumer buying behavior. In this context, it is crucial to explore the impact of social media on impulsive buying behavior within the community of Mataram City. A case study on the residents of Mataram City will provide a deeper understanding of how social media influences consumer purchasing decisions within the city's environment.

By exploring the influence of social media on impulsive buying behavior in Mataram City, this research will provide new insights for marketers, businesses, and researchers to develop more effective marketing strategies in the era of social media. Furthermore, this research can also help consumers become more aware of the impact of social media on their purchasing decisions and enhance consumer intelligence in this digital age. Hence, this research holds significant relevance and importance in examining the impact of social media on impulsive buying behavior in the community of Mataram City, as well as contributing to both academic and practical knowledge in the field of digital marketing.

2. Literature Review

2.1. Online Impulsive Buying

Online impulsive buying is a phenomenon where consumers make spontaneous and unplanned purchases while shopping in the online environment. According to Rook (1987), impulsive buying is an unplanned and sudden purchase triggered by external or emotional stimuli. Meanwhile, Beatty & Ferrell (1998) regard impulsive buying as behavior influenced by hedonic desires. These opinions depict marketing experts' perspectives on the factors that influence online impulsive buying, including interactions within the online environment, emotional factors, and the influence of social media.

2.2. Hedonic Motivation

Hedonic motivation is a psychological drive that encourages individuals to seek pleasure, emotional satisfaction, or joy in consumption behavior. Hirschman & Holbrook (1982) introduced the concept of "hedonic consumption" and argued that pleasurable and satisfying consumption experiences are the primary goals of consumers. They described that hedonic satisfaction can be attained through sensory stimulation, aesthetics, and social interaction. This statement provides insights into the significance of hedonic motivation in consumption behavior. This drive can influence how consumers perceive products, shopping experiences, and the ultimate goals of their consumption.

2.3. Attractiveness

Attractiveness is a factor that influences the appeal and interest of individuals towards a product, brand, or service. Kahle & Homer (1985) focused their perspective on the aspect of attractiveness in advertising and marketing communication. They argued that attraction to advertisements can affect consumers' perceptions of the advertised products. This concept affects how individuals perceive products, brands, and services, as well as how this influence can impact their purchasing decisions.

2.4. Electronic Word of Mouth

Electronic Word of Mouth is the process where individuals share experiences, opinions, or recommendations about products, brands, or services online through platforms such as social media, product reviews, or discussion forums. Hennig-Thurau et al., (2004) define Electronic Word of Mouth as any form of positive or negative communication between individuals through electronic platforms. Kozinets (1999) highlights that within online communities, Electronic Word of Mouth can form a "brand community" where members share information and experiences about specific brands and products. This concept reflects how online interactions can influence consumers' perceptions and behaviors towards brands and products.

2.5. Trustworthiness

Trustworthiness is a key factor in building a positive relationship between consumers and brands, products, or services. Moorman et al., (1993) argue that consumers tend to trust brands perceived to have quality, integrity, and benevolence towards them. Garbarino & Johnson (1999) suggest that when a brand consistently delivers expected outcomes to consumers, trust in that brand will grow. Dimensions like ability, integrity, and benevolence play a crucial role in influencing consumer perceptions and purchase decisions.

2.6. Website Quality

Website quality is a factor that influences user experience and consumer perceptions of a website. Parasuraman et al., (2005) posit that website quality encompasses several dimensions such as reliability, responsiveness, user-friendliness, and aesthetics. They emphasize that a positive user experience can enhance customer satisfaction and loyalty towards the website. Consumers are more likely to return to websites that are perceived to have good quality.

3. Research Method

The research approach employed is a quantitative approach. This research is a causal associative that examines the influence of social media variables on online impulsive buying. The research is focused on the community in Mataram City.

The population in this research consists of all residents of Mataram City who engage in online shopping and consistently use e-commerce platforms for their purchases. The sampling method used is non-probability sampling with purposive sampling technique, which involves intentionally selecting samples. The exact size of the population sample is unknown; thus, the sample size is determined to be 100 respondent samples.

The data collection tool used in this research is an online questionnaire. The questionnaire presented in this research consists of statements about the influence of social media variables on online impulsive buying among the community in Mataram City. The questionnaire is distributed to respondents online through Google Form.

The statistical analysis technique employed in this research utilizes the assistance of SPSS 26 software. The analysis includes the first testing, which is the Classical Assumption Test, comprising tests for Normality, Multicollinearity, and Heteroscedasticity. The second testing involves the Multiple Linear Regression Test, the third testing encompasses Hypothesis Testing comprising t-tests and F-tests, and the fourth testing is the Coefficient of Determination Test.

4. Results and Discussion

4.1. Data Analysis

Here is a table of frequency distribution scores for the research variables, which include Hedonic Motivation, Attractiveness, Electronic Word of Mouth, Trustworthiness, Website Quality, and Impulsive Buying.

TABLE I. FREQUENCY DISTRIBUTION SCORES

Variable	Score	Criteria
Hedonic Motivation (X ₁)	2.65	Fairly Good
Attractiveness (X ₂)	3.06	Fairly Good
E-Word of Mouth (X ₃)	2.81	Fairly Good
Trustworthiness (X ₄)	4.04	Good
Website Quality (X ₅)	3.84	Good
Impulsive Buying (Y)	3.99	Good

Source: data analysis results.

Based on Table I, it can be explained that respondents using e-commerce platforms for shopping are fairly interested in the Hedonic Motivation variable. This is evident from the respondents' answer scores on the questionnaire, which amount to 2.65, falling within the fairly good criteria range, which is between 2.61 and 3.40. This indicates that consumers using e-commerce platforms for shopping are fairly interested in the Hedonic Motivation present in social media.

It can be observed that respondents using e-commerce platforms for shopping state that Attractiveness is considered fairly attractive. This is evident from the respondents' answer scores on the questionnaire, which amount to 3.06, falling within the criteria range of fairly good, which is between 2.61 and 3.40. Respondents feel satisfied with the Attractiveness of each e-commerce platform in conveying the products and services offered through social media.

Next, the responses of respondents as users of e-commerce platforms for shopping towards the Electronic Word of Mouth variable are considered to be fairly good. This is evident from the average score of respondents' answers on the questionnaire, which is 2.81, falling within the criteria range of fairly good, between 2.61 and 3.40. Respondents using e-commerce platforms for shopping have fairly good responses towards the indicators of the Electronic Word of Mouth variable.

The assessment of respondents as users of e-commerce platforms for shopping is considered good towards the Trustworthiness variable. This is evident from the average score of respondents' answers on the questionnaire, which is 4.04, falling within the criteria range of good, between 3.41 and 4.20. This means that consumers using e-commerce platforms for shopping trust the e-commerce and social media used by manufacturers in offering their products and services.

Meanwhile, the assessment of respondents as users of e-commerce platforms for shopping on the Website Quality variable falls under the category of good. This is evident from the average score of respondents' answers on the questionnaire, which is 3.84, falling within the criteria range of good (between 3.41 and 4.20). Respondents using e-commerce platforms for shopping have a positive response towards the Website Quality.

On the other hand, the responses of respondents as users of e-commerce platforms for shopping towards the Impulsive Buying variable are considered good. This is evident from the average score of respondents' answers on the questionnaire, which is 3.99, falling within the criteria range of good, which is between 3.41 and 4.20. This indicates that respondents using e-commerce platforms for shopping have a positive response towards the Impulsive Buying.

Here is the table of questionnaire validity test results using the SPSS software:

TABLE II. RESEARCH QUESTIONNAIRE VALIDITY TEST RESULTS

Item	r Value	r Critical	Criteria
X _{1.1}	0.812	0.300	Valid
X _{1.2}	0.711	0.300	Valid
X _{1.3}	0.999	0.300	Valid
X _{2.1}	0.487	0.300	Valid
X _{2.2}	0.770	0.300	Valid
X _{2.3}	0.660	0.300	Valid
X _{3.1}	0.867	0.300	Valid
X _{3.2}	0.478	0.300	Valid
X _{3.3}	0.880	0.300	Valid
X _{4.1}	0.844	0.300	Valid
X _{4.2}	0.774	0.300	Valid
X _{4.3}	0.781	0.300	Valid
X _{5.1}	0.517	0.300	Valid
X _{5.2}	0.805	0.300	Valid
X _{5.3}	0.331	0.300	Valid
Y _{1.1}	0.781	0.300	Valid
Y _{1.2}	0.517	0.300	Valid
Y _{1.3}	0.805	0.300	Valid

Source: data analysis results.

Based on the results of the instrument validity test, it can be seen that the values of all item questions are greater than 0.300, indicating that

all instrument items are considered valid. In other words, the calculated r-value is greater than the critical r-value, which means the questionnaire is valid. The indicator items of social media, which include Hedonic Motivation, Attractiveness, Electronic Word of Mouth, Trustworthiness, and Website Quality, as well as the Impulsive Buying variable used in this research questionnaire, are able to measure the responses of respondents who are users of e-commerce platforms for shopping on the community in Mataram City.

Next, for testing the instrument's reliability in this research, Cronbach's alpha was used. Below is a summary of the results of the instrument's reliability test for each research variable.

TABLE III. RESEARCH QUESTIONNAIRE RELIABILITY TEST RESULTS

Variable	Alpha Cronbach	Alpha Critical	Criteria
Hedonic Motivation (X ₁)	0.803	0.600	Reliable
Attractiveness (X ₂)	0.999	0.600	Reliable
E-Word of Mouth (X ₃)	0.725	0.600	Reliable
Trustworthiness (X ₄)	0.807	0.600	Reliable
Website Quality (X ₅)	0.839	0.600	Reliable
Impulsive Buying (Y)	0.755	0.600	Reliable

Source: data analysis results.

Based on the data in the table above, it can be observed that all variables have Cronbach's Alpha values greater than 0.600. This indicates that the social media variables, including Hedonic Motivation, Attractiveness, Electronic Word of Mouth, Trustworthiness, and Website Quality, as well as the Impulsive Buying variable in this research, are considered reliable.

As mentioned in Chapter 3, classical assumption tests were conducted on the data to generate the best regression equation model, also known as the Best Linear Unbiased Estimator (BLUE). The classical assumption tests that will be conducted in the research regarding the influence of social media variables including Hedonic Motivation, Attractiveness, Electronic Word of Mouth, Trustworthiness, and Website Quality on the formation of Impulsive Buying in the community of Mataram City.

The normality test is performed to determine whether the research model of the influence of social media on the formation of Impulsive Buying in the community of Mataram follows a normal distribution. In this research, the non-parametric Kolmogorov-Smirnov (K-S) statistical test is used. The results of whether the residuals are normally distributed or not can be seen in the following Table IV:

TABLE IV. NORMALITY TEST RESULTS

		Unstandardized Residual
N		100
Normal Parameters ^{a,b}	Mean	0.000000
	Std. Deviation	0.08714988
Most Extreme Differences	Absolute	0.082
	Positive	0.073
	Negative	-0.082
Kolmogorov-Smirnov Z		0.582
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)		0.888

Source: data analysis results.

Based on the results in Table IV, it can be observed that the value of Kolmogorov-Smirnov (K-S) for the research model of the influence of social media on the formation of Impulsive Buying in the community of Mataram City is 0.582 with a probability of 0.888, which is far above the 5 percent alpha level. Therefore, it can be concluded that the data in this research already exhibit a normal distribution.

The purpose of the multicollinearity test is to determine whether the independent variables of social media, including Hedonic Motivation, Attractiveness, Electronic Word of Mouth, Trustworthiness, and Website Quality, are linearly related to each other. If there is no significant relationship among the independent variables used, it can be stated that there is no multicollinearity. The multicollinearity test is conducted using the values of Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) and tolerance. The results of the multicollinearity analysis can be seen in the following Table V:

TABLE V. MULTICOLLINEARITY TEST RESULTS

Model	Collinearity Statistics	
	Tolerance	VIF
(Constant)		
Hedonic Motivation (X ₁)	0.743	1.346
Attractiveness (X ₂)	0.681	1.469
E-Word of Mouth (X ₃)	0.545	1.836
Trustworthiness (X ₄)	0.643	1.554
Website Quality (X ₅)	0.550	1.818

Source: data analysis results.

Based on Table V, it can be seen that the tolerance value for each variable is greater than 0.010, while the Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) values for each variable are less than 10. Therefore, it can be stated that the model used in the research does not indicate the presence of multicollinearity.

An important assumption in linear regression is that the disturbances in the regression model exhibit homoskedasticity, meaning that all disturbances have equal variance. In regression, heteroskedasticity may occur. The heteroskedasticity test aims to determine whether there is inequality of variance in the residuals between observations in the regression model of the influence of social media, including Hedonic Motivation, Attractiveness, Electronic Word of Mouth, Trustworthiness, and Website Quality, on the formation of Impulsive Buying in the community of Mataram City. The heteroskedasticity test is conducted using the Glejser test as a statistical method. The results of the heteroskedasticity analysis can be seen in the following Table VI:

TABLE VI. HETEROSKEDASTICITY TEST RESULTS

Model	t	Sig.
(Constant)	1.503	0.140
Hedonic Motivation (X ₁)	-0.610	0.545
Attractiveness (X ₂)	0.425	0.673
E-Word of Mouth (X ₃)	-0.866	0.391
Trustworthiness (X ₄)	0.237	0.814
Website Quality (X ₅)	-1.249	0.218

Source: data analysis results.

The results of the heteroskedasticity test in Table VI indicate that no independent variable significantly affects the dependent variable's absolute residual value. This is evident from the non-significant probability above the 5 percent confidence level. Therefore, it can be stated that heteroskedasticity does not occur in the research data regarding the influence of social media, including Hedonic Motivation, Attractiveness, Electronic Word of Mouth, Trustworthiness, and Website Quality, on the formation of Impulsive Buying in the community of Mataram City.

Next, to analyze the data, multiple linear regression analysis is used, preceded by formulating whether the model meets the requirements or not. This is based on Table VII:

TABLE VII. RESEARCH MODEL: THE INFLUENCE OF SOCIAL MEDIA ON ONLINE IMPULSIVE BUYING

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	
	B	Std. Error	Beta			
						(Constant)
1	X1	0.055	0.031	0.040	1.751	0.087
	X2	0.078	0.018	0.102	4.231	0.000
	X3	0.082	0.034	0.065	2.397	0.021
	X4	0.816	0.022	0.939	37.894	0.000
	X5	0.200	0.019	0.287	10.717	0.000

Source: data analysis results.

From Table VII above, the regression coefficients of the research variables are presented and can be explained as follows:

$$Y = 0,684 + 0,055 X_1 + 0,078 X_2 + 0,082 X_3 + 0,816 X_4 + 0,200 X_5$$

- 1) The constant value of 0.684 indicates that the average score of Impulsive Buying in the community of Mataram City is 0.684 when the manufacturing company does not implement social media consisting of Hedonic Motivation, Attractiveness, Electronic Word of Mouth, Trustworthiness, and Website Quality. This implies that Impulsive Buying in the community of Mataram City shows a very low level, so without the implementation of social media, the formation of Impulsive Buying in the community of Mataram City would be very low.
- 2) The influence of the Hedonic Motivation variable (X1) on the formation of Impulsive Buying (Y) in the community of Mataram City, based on calculations using the SPSS program, resulted in a regression coefficient value of 0.055. The positive sign indicates a positive or direct relationship. This means that for every increase of 1 unit in the Hedonic Motivation variable, Impulsive Buying will increase by 0.055 units, assuming Attractiveness, Electronic Word of Mouth, Trustworthiness, and Website Quality are considered constant or unchanged. From the analysis conducted, it can be stated that the higher the Hedonic Motivation variable, the higher the Impulsive Buying. Conversely, if there is a decrease in Hedonic Motivation, it will also decrease Impulsive Buying.
- 3) The influence of the Attractiveness (X2) on the formation of Impulsive Buying (Y), based on calculations, resulted in a regression coefficient value of 0.078. The positive sign indicates a positive or direct relationship. This means that for every increase of 1 unit in the Attractiveness, Impulsive Buying will increase by 0.078 units, assuming Hedonic Motivation, Electronic Word of Mouth, Trustworthiness, and Website Quality are considered constant or unchanged. From the analysis conducted, it can be stated that the higher the Attractiveness variable, the higher the Impulsive Buying. Conversely, if there is a decrease in Attractiveness, it will also decrease Impulsive Buying.
- 4) The influence of Electronic Word of Mouth (X3) on Impulsive Buying (Y) resulted in a regression coefficient value of 0.082. The positive sign indicates a positive or direct relationship. This means that for every increase of 1 unit in the Electronic Word of Mouth, Impulsive Buying will increase by 0.123 units, assuming Hedonic Motivation, Attractiveness, Trustworthiness, and Website Quality are considered constant or unchanged. From the analysis conducted, it can be stated that the higher the Electronic Word of Mouth, the higher the Impulsive Buying. Conversely, if there is a decrease in Electronic Word of Mouth, it will also decrease Impulsive Buying.
- 5) The influence of Trustworthiness (X4) on Impulsive Buying (Y) resulted in a regression coefficient value of 0.816. The positive sign indicates a positive or direct relationship. This means that for every increase of 1 unit in the Trustworthiness variable, Impulsive

Buying will increase by 0.816 units, assuming Hedonic Motivation, Attractiveness, Electronic Word of Mouth, and Website Quality are considered constant or unchanged. From the analysis conducted, it can be stated that the higher the Trustworthiness, the higher the Impulsive Buying. Conversely, if there is a decrease in Trustworthiness, it will also decrease Impulsive Buying.

- 6) The influence of the Website Quality variable (X5) on Impulsive Buying (Y) based on the analysis resulted in a regression coefficient value of 0.200. The positive sign indicates a positive or direct relationship. This means that for every increase of 1 unit in the Website Quality variable, Impulsive Buying will increase by 0.200 units, assuming Hedonic Motivation, Attractiveness, Electronic Word of Mouth, and Trustworthiness are considered constant or unchanged. From the analysis conducted, it can be stated that the higher the Website Quality, the higher the Impulsive Buying. Conversely, if there is a decrease in Website Quality, it will also decrease Impulsive Buying.

To test the presence or absence of the role of the independent variables of social media, which consist of Hedonic Motivation, Attractiveness, Electronic Word of Mouth, Trustworthiness, and Website Quality, in influencing the formation of Impulsive Buying in the community of Mataram city, the F-test is conducted. The results of the F-test calculations using SPSS are presented below:

TABLE VIII. F TEST RESULTS

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1 Regression	21.012	5	4.202	496.855	0.000 ^b
Residual	0.752	94	0.008		
Total	21.764	99			

Source: data analysis results.

From Table VIII, it can be observed that the calculated F-value is 496.855 with a significance level of 0.000. In comparison to the tabulated F-value derived from a table with a 5 percent significance level and degrees of freedom $df_1 = 5$ and $df_2 = 94$, the tabulated F-value is found to be 2.430. As the calculated F-value (496.855) is greater than the tabulated F-value, the null hypothesis (H_0) is rejected and the alternative hypothesis (H_a) is accepted. This means that the variables of social media, including Hedonic Motivation, Attractiveness, Electronic Word of Mouth, Trustworthiness, and Website Quality, collectively have a significant influence on the formation of Impulsive Buying in the community of Mataram city.

The t-test is used to assess the significance of the influence of each individual variable within the set of social media variables, which include Hedonic Motivation, Attractiveness, Electronic Word of Mouth, Trustworthiness, and Website Quality, on the formation of Impulsive Buying in the community of Mataram city. The results of the t-test and the significance level of each independent variable on the dependent variable can be seen in Table IX:

TABLE IX. T VALUE AND SIGNIFICATIONS TEST RESULTS

Variable	t Value	p Value	Criteria
Hedonic Motivation (X ₁)	1,751	0,087	Insignificant
Attractiveness (X ₂)	4,231	0,000	Significant
E-Word of Mouth (X ₃)	2,397	0,021	Significant
Trustworthiness (X ₄)	37,894	0,000	Significant
Website Quality (X ₅)	10,717	0,000	Significant

Source: data analysis results.

For a clearer understanding, the meanings of the analysis results for each variable, namely Hedonic Motivation, Attractiveness, Electronic Word of Mouth, Trustworthiness, and Website Quality, in relation to the

formation of Impulsive Buying in the community of Mataram city, will be elaborated as follows:

- 1) The level of significance of the variable Hedonic Motivation (X1) on the formation of Impulsive Buying (Y) in the community of Mataram city resulted in a t-value of 1.751 with a significance value of 0.087. When the t-value of 1.751 is compared with the t-table value of 2.009, the t-value is smaller than the t-table value, indicating that H_a is rejected and H_0 is accepted. This can also be observed from the comparison of the achieved significance value of 0.087, which means the error rate is higher than 5 percent. Thus, the variable Hedonic Motivation has an insignificant influence on the formation of Impulsive Buying in the community of Mataram city. The positive value indicates a positive relationship or direct proportion. This means that the higher the Hedonic Motivation, the higher the Impulsive Buying and conversely, if Hedonic Motivation is low, it will decrease Impulsive Buying.
- 2) The level of significance of the variable Attractiveness (X2) on the formation of Impulsive Buying (Y) in the community of Mataram city resulted in a t-value of 4.231 with a significance value of 0.000. When the t-value of 4.231 is compared with the t-table value of 2.009, the t-value is larger than the t-table value, indicating that H_a is accepted and H_0 is rejected. This can also be observed from the comparison of the achieved significance value of 0.000, which means the error rate is lower than 5 percent. Thus, the variable Attractiveness has a significant influence on the formation of Impulsive Buying in the community of Mataram city. The positive value indicates a positive relationship or direct proportion. This means that the higher the Attractiveness, the higher the Impulsive Buying and conversely, if Attractiveness is low, it will decrease Impulsive Buying.
- 3) The level of significance of the variable Electronic Word of Mouth (X3) on the formation of Impulsive Buying (Y) resulted in a t-value of 2.397 with a significance value of 0.021. When the t-value of 2.397 is compared with the t-table value of 2.009, the t-value is larger than the t-table value, indicating that H_0 is rejected and H_a is accepted. This can also be observed from the comparison of the achieved significance value of 0.021, which means the error rate is lower than 5 percent. Thus, the variable Electronic Word of Mouth has a significant influence on the formation of Impulsive Buying. The higher the Electronic Word of Mouth, the higher the Impulsive Buying and conversely, if Electronic Word of Mouth is low, it will decrease Impulsive Buying.
- 4) The level of significance of the variable Trustworthiness (X4) on the formation of Impulsive Buying (Y) resulted in a t-value of 37.894 with a significance value of 0.000. When the t-value of 37.894 is compared with the t-table value of 2.009, the t-value is larger than the t-table value, indicating that H_0 is rejected and H_a is accepted. This can also be observed from the comparison of the achieved significance value of 0.000, which means the error rate is lower than 5 percent. Thus, the variable Trustworthiness has a significant influence on the formation of Impulsive Buying. The higher the Trustworthiness, the higher the Impulsive Buying and conversely, if Trustworthiness is low, it will decrease Impulsive Buying.
- 5) The level of significance of the variable Website Quality (X5) on the formation of Impulsive Buying (Y) resulted in a t-value of 10.717 with a significance value of 0.000. When the t-value of 10.717 is compared with the t-table value of 2.009, the t-value is larger than the t-table value, indicating that H_0 is rejected and H_a is accepted. This can also be observed from the comparison of the achieved significance value of 0.000, which means the error rate is lower than 5 percent. Thus, the variable Website Quality has a significant influence on the formation of Impulsive Buying in the community

of Mataram city. The higher the Website Quality, the higher the Impulsive Buying and conversely, if Website Quality is low, it will decrease Impulsive Buying.

From the multiple regression model, it can be concluded that the variable that significantly influences the formation of Impulsive Buying in the community of Mataram city is Trustworthiness (X4). This is based on the highest t-value (37.894) compared to the variables Hedonic Motivation (X1), Attractiveness (X2), Electronic Word of Mouth (X3), and Website Quality (X5). Thus, the hypothesis stating that Trustworthiness is the dominant variable influencing the formation of Impulsive Buying is proven in this research.

The coefficient of determination (R^2) essentially measures how well the model explains the variation in the independent variables. From the calculations using the SPSS program, the following results are obtained:

TABLE X. DETERMINATION COEFFICIENT (R^2)

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	0.991 ^a	0.983	0.981	0.09197

Source: data analysis results.

Based on Table X, the multiple linear regression coefficient of determination (Adjusted R^2) is obtained as 0.981 or 98.10 percent. This means that the social media variables consisting of Hedonic Motivation, Attractiveness, Electronic Word of Mouth, Trustworthiness, and Website Quality contribute or account for 98.10 percent in shaping Impulsive Buying in the community of Mataram city. The remaining 1.90 percent is attributed to other variables outside the scope of the research.

4.2. Research Findings and Discussions

Based on the research findings, it is concluded that the social media variables consisting of Hedonic Motivation, Attractiveness, Electronic Word of Mouth, Trustworthiness, and Website Quality have a significant influence on the formation of Impulsive Buying in the community of Mataram city. This is supported by the analysis of the multiple coefficient of determination, which is obtained as 0.981 or 98.10 percent. This means that the social media variables consisting of Hedonic Motivation, Attractiveness, Electronic Word of Mouth, Trustworthiness, and Website Quality contribute or account for 98.10 percent in shaping Impulsive Buying in the community of Mataram city. The remaining 1.90 percent is influenced by other variables beyond the scope of the research.

Based on the review of previous research, it can be observed that this research further strengthens the viewpoints proposed by Rook (1987) as well as Beatty & Ferrell (1998), stating that social media variables comprising Hedonic Motivation (Hirschman & Holbrook, 1982), Attractiveness (Kahle & Homer, 1985), Electronic Word of Mouth (Hennig-Thurau et al., 2004; Kozinets, 1999), Trustworthiness (Moorman et al., 1993; Garbarino & Johnson, 1999), and Website Quality (Parasuraman et al., 2005) have a simultaneous significant influence on Impulsive Buying. The findings of this research are also consistent with previous research conducted by Chen (2022); Aslam (2021); Budree et al., (2021); Meiselwitz (2021); Zafar et al., (2019); Aragoncillo & Orus (2018), where it has been demonstrated that social media has a significant impact on Impulsive Buying.

Partially, each independent variable of social media has an influence on the formation of Impulsive Buying in the community of Mataram city. Based on the data analysis, the results show that there is a positive or directional relationship between social media and Impulsive Buying. This indicates that if there is a change, such as an increase, in the social media variable, it will also lead to a corresponding change (increase) in the Impulsive Buying variable. This is supported by the positive coefficients of the regression analysis.

The Hedonic Motivation variable has a non-significant influence on the formation of Impulsive Buying among the residents of Mataram city. Thus, the first hypothesis (H₁) put forth cannot be accepted. The results of this research indicate that Hedonic Motivation does not significantly affect the formation of Impulsive Buying.

The lack of significant influence of the Hedonic Motivation variable on the formation of online Impulsive Buying could be attributed to several possible reasons, such as sample characteristics and the research context. Individuals participating in the research might not prioritize hedonic motivation as a significant factor in their impulsive buying behavior. People's motivations for impulsive buying can vary based on personal preferences, cultural factors, and other individual characteristics. The specific context or nature of the products or services being studied might not strongly align with hedonic motivations. If the products or services being considered are more utilitarian in nature rather than driven by hedonistic desires, the impact of hedonic motivation on impulsive buying might be diminished.

It's important to note that the absence of significant influence in one research does not necessarily mean that the variable has no influence in all situations. The results could vary based on the specific context, sample characteristics, and research methods used. Further investigation, replication of the research, and exploring the factors mentioned above could provide a clearer understanding of why the Hedonic Motivation variable didn't show a significant impact in this particular study.

The Attractiveness variable has a significant influence on the formation of Impulsive Buying among the residents of Mataram city. The research findings reveal a strong correlation between the Attractiveness variable and Impulsive Buying behavior within the population of Mataram city. These findings further reinforce the results of the research conducted by Varghese & Chitra (2022) and Koay et al., (2021), which stated that attractiveness significantly influences online Impulsive Buying.

In this context, Attractiveness refers to the visual appeal, aesthetics, and appealing elements associated with products or services. These findings indicate that consumers' interest in the visual and aesthetic aspects of a product or service positively influences the inclination to engage in online Impulsive Buying. The implication is that in online marketing efforts, companies and e-commerce platforms need to consider design elements, visual presentation, and other captivating factors to effectively attract consumers and drive higher levels of impulsive purchasing.

The Electronic Word of Mouth variable has a significant influence on the formation of online Impulsive Buying among the residents of Mataram city. The research findings indicate a strong positive correlation between the Electronic Word of Mouth variable and Impulsive Buying behavior. These findings have confirmed the results of research conducted by Koay et al., (2021), Sharma (2020), and Kazi et al., (2019), which indicate that Electronic Word of Mouth significantly influences customers' online Impulsive Buying behavior.

Electronic Word of Mouth refers to information, reviews, and recommendations communicated through online platforms, such as social media, forums, and websites. These findings suggest that consumers are likely to be influenced by positive reviews and experiences they read or hear from others when making impulsive purchasing decisions. The implication is that marketing strategies that incorporate positive Electronic Word of Mouth promotions can enhance the attractiveness of products or services and stimulate higher levels of Impulsive Buying behavior. In the current digital environment, it's crucial for companies to effectively leverage the influence of Electronic Word of Mouth in their efforts to impact consumer behavior.

The Trustworthiness variable has a significant impact on the formation of Impulsive Buying behavior among the residents of

Mataram city. The research findings indicate a strong correlation between the Trustworthiness variable and the tendency to engage in Impulsive Buying. Similarly to the findings in the research by Varghese & Chitra (2022), Koay et al., (2021), Kazi et al., (2019), it is indicated that Trustworthiness in social media marketing can effectively enhance the level of Impulsive Buying behavior.

In this context, trust refers to the level of confidence that consumers have in the brand, seller, or e-commerce platform they interact with. These findings suggest that a high level of trust in online information sources or offers can influence consumers to make impulsive purchases with the belief that they will receive products or services that meet their expectations. The implication is that building and maintaining consumer trust in the online environment is crucial for stimulating higher levels of Impulsive Buying behavior. In marketing strategies and consumer interactions, companies should focus on building a positive trust image to optimize the influence of the Trustworthiness variable on Impulsive Buying behavior formation.

The Website Quality variable significantly influences the formation of Impulsive Buying behavior among the residents of Mataram city. The research findings demonstrate a strong positive correlation between the Website Quality and Impulsive Buying behavior. These findings further reinforce the results of the research conducted by Varghese & Chitra (2022), Bansal & Kumar (2018), Al-Zyoud (2018) suggests that Website Quality significantly affects users' online Impulsive Buying behavior on social media platforms.

Website quality refers to aspects such as design, navigation, speed, and functionality of the website in presenting information and products to consumers. These findings indicate that consumers who have a positive experience while interacting with a high-quality website are more inclined to engage in online impulsive purchases. The implication is that in the digital environment, companies should ensure that their websites are well-designed and provide a satisfying user experience to enhance the likelihood of higher Impulsive Buying behavior. In the effort to maximize the influence of the Website Quality variable, it is crucial to continuously monitor and enhance the user experience when interacting with their online platforms.

From the t-test results, it can also be determined which independent variable has the most dominant influence on the formation of Impulsive Buying behavior among the residents of Mataram city, by comparing the values of each t-statistic for each independent variable. Thus, the independent variable with the highest t-statistic value is the one that has the most dominant influence, which in this case is the Trustworthiness variable with a t-statistic value of 37.894. This means that if the Trustworthiness variable can be further increased, it can lead to an increase in Impulsive Buying behavior. This finding aligns with the proposed hypothesis, where Trustworthiness has a dominant impact on Impulsive Buying behavior.

5. Conclusion

Based on the conducted data analysis, it can be concluded that simultaneously, social media variables consisting of Hedonic Motivation, Attractiveness, Electronic Word of Mouth, Trustworthiness, and Website Quality have a significant impact on the formation of Impulsive Buying behavior in the community of Mataram city. However, individually, only Hedonic Motivation does not have a significant influence on online Impulsive Buying. Meanwhile, Trustworthiness is the variable with dominant influence.

In summary, this research underscores the multifaceted nature of social media's impact on online impulsive buying behavior. Tailoring marketing efforts to enhance the individual components and recognizing the pivotal role of trustworthiness can contribute to a more effective engagement with consumers in Mataram city. Further exploration of the

nuanced interplay between hedonic motivations and impulsive buying behavior can provide deeper insights into consumer decision-making processes.

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